

Internship report

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Constraining the Spatial Curvature of the Universe thanks to its Large-Scale Structure

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Abstract

In this work, we study the detectability of potential spatial curvature of the universe with the Euclid satellite. We begin by establishing the theoretical framework, presenting the general expression for the correlation function in both flat and curved space, while also accounting for wide-angle effects. Notably, we show that, in the flat regime, the ratio dipole-to-quadrupole simplifies to the expression $\frac{3}{5} \frac{r}{r_1}$ under the assumption that the comoving distance between surveyed objects r is much smaller than their radial comoving distance r_1 . Therefore, the ratio is used to survey the Euclid mock catalogues as they don't include curvature. The comparison and the good matching between the empirical ratio and the theoretical one across different values of r allows first to retrieve the flatness of the catalogues, validating the theoretical model, and then to set the superior limit of this model to r approximately equal to $70 h^{-1} Mpc$. Moreover, by analysing the errors of these measurements, it appears that at least 2 observations are needed to ensure the detectability of the ratio, meaning that the Euclid satellite will need to survey a volume twice larger than the one actually surveyed to properly detect the ratio and eventually look for deviations from its expected evolution in flatness regime to gain insights into potential curvature. Finally, this ratio is exploited to test cosmologies with different values of $\Omega_{m,0}$. Among the ones tested, the $\Omega_{m,0} = 0.32$ cosmology is the best fit to the theoretical prediction.

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1 Introduction

The standard model of cosmology, commonly referred to as the Λ CDM model, is grounded in the Friedmann–Lemaître–Robertson–Walker (FLRW) framework, which describes a universe that is expanding, isotropic, and homogeneous on large scales. In this model, Λ represents the cosmological constant, a mysterious force behind the universe’s accelerated expansion and a major contributor to the overall energy budget. The "CDM" in Λ CDM stands for cold dark matter, which constitutes the predominant form of matter in the universe, accounting for most of the remaining cosmic energy budget. While radiation is often considered negligible in this context, a fourth component can also be considered when evaluating the total energy content of the universe, and its spatial curvature.

In the Λ CDM model, the universe is assumed to be flat, setting to zero the curvature density parameter $\Omega_K = -K/(aH)^2$, which quantifies the contribution of spatial curvature to the overall energy density of the universe and where K is the curvature parameter ($=-1, 0$ or 1 corresponding to open, flat, and closed universes, respectively), a the scale factor and H the Hubble parameter. This is due to different observations that estimated the value of Ω_K within a range that didn’t exclude a perfect flatness, with for instance the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) anisotropy data obtained from the Wilkinson Microwave Anisotropy Probe (WMAP) that resulted into $\Omega_K = -0.037^{+0.044}_{-0.042}$ at a confidence level of 68 % [7]. Moreover, Λ CDM fits very well these data and shows no evidence for deviations from the model including non-zero curvature [2]. Adding to this the fact that most of the inflationary models predict a negligible present time curvature and the additional complexity when addressing the large scale structure in a curved space results in an ideal environment for using the perfectly flat Λ CDM without the need of having concerns about any curvature. Thus Λ CDM has been the main model for studying the large scale structure. However, data delivered from the satellite Planck in 2018 [12] on temperature and polarization anisotropies of the CMB allowed to narrow the range of possible values of Ω_K and more especially to disadvantage the flatness scenario, as the estimation from this device was $\Omega_K = -0.056^{+0.028}_{-0.018}$ at a confidence level of 68 %. This gave rise to a “curvature tension” as Planck 2018 dataset favors a curved space in contradiction with the rest of the datasets from other observations. It’s worth mentioning that the Planck satellite surveyed larger scales in comparison with older devices, leaving room for the possibility that only the patch of the universe that we could survey until then was flat, but when considering larger scales, the effects of an eventual underlying curvature would become more noticeable.

With this being said, it becomes important to get ready to interpret properly the data to come from next generation telescopes knowing that they will survey the ultra-large scale structure, that is further than ever, to try to better constrain spatial curvature. Even though it can be argued that an eventual curvature wouldn’t be significant, it’s still worth it to address it to characterize more precisely the cosmic energy budget distribution. Also, curvature, as small as it has been inferred from Planck 2018 dataset, has been shown to reduce the tension on the hubble parameter [13]. A curved space wouldn’t compromise the inflation theory, it rather would help us gain insights into the right inflationary model, making it even more interesting to study this tension.

One of the next generation instruments surveying the ultra large scale structure is the Euclid satellite, which was launched in July 2023, and will release its first data mapping the cosmic web in December 2024. A major tool into analysing the cosmic web as it will be captured by Euclid is the two point correlation function, which is a way of

quantifying matter clustering over a given scale (more on this in the second chapter). An important work has been done in [9] to take into account spatial curvature in the correlation function, while [4] studied how this function would be affected by curvature in different configurations comparatively to the flat case, and in which case the effects would be significant. The goal of my internship was to use the correlation function to analyse the Euclid mock data and to figure out under which conditions eventual curvature effects would be detectable.

The report is structured as follows: the second chapter provides an introduction to the fundamentals of large-scale structure cosmology, with a focus on the effects that manifest in redshift space. It also introduces wide-angle effects before detailing the theoretical framework used in this study, specifically the correlation function that accounts for wide-angle effects and the dipole-to-quadrupole ratio within a flat universe. The third chapter describes the methodology employed to generate the Euclid mock data, while the fourth one discusses the development and testing of the counting algorithm. The final section presents the core findings of this study, including the measurements of the ratio in the mock catalogues, its detectability, and the Alcock-Paczyński test using this ratio, along with discussion.

2 Theoretical model

2.1 Contextualisation

In cosmology, the density field $\rho(\mathbf{x})$ is a fundamental concept used to describe the distribution of matter across the universe, assigning a mass density value to each point in space [8]. This field, while often modeled as continuous on large scales, emerges from the discrete nature of mass distribution at smaller scales, such as galaxies and clusters. To explore deviations from the average cosmic density, $\bar{\rho}$, cosmologists introduce the overdensity field, $\delta(\mathbf{x})$, defined as

$$\delta(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\rho(\mathbf{x}) - \bar{\rho}}{\bar{\rho}}.$$

This field highlights regions of over and under density relative to the cosmic average, providing insights into the gravitational clustering that drives structure formation. By its definition, the average value of the overdensity field over the universe is zero, $\langle \delta(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = 0$, because the deviations from the mean, by their very nature, sum to zero when averaged over the entire field. This zero-mean property simplifies the mathematical treatment of the field and is foundational in the statistical analysis of cosmological data.

To understand the scale of density fluctuations, we examine the variance of the overdensity field,

$$\sigma^2 = \langle \delta^2(\mathbf{x}) \rangle - \langle \delta(\mathbf{x}) \rangle^2 = \langle \delta^2(\mathbf{x}) \rangle,$$

which quantifies the spread or dispersion of density fluctuations around the mean. The variance concept here can be further used to assess density fluctuations in two different points in space, defining therefore the two point correlation function

$$\xi(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) = \langle \delta(\mathbf{x}_1)\delta(\mathbf{x}_2) \rangle,$$

which measures how the density at one point correlates with the density at another point. This function represents the excess probability, compared to a random distribution, of finding pairs of points (e.g., galaxies) separated by a given distance. Assuming the universe

Figure 1: Matter power spectrum as determined from different surveys [12].

is both isotropic and homogeneous, which posits that the statistical properties of the universe are the same in all directions and locations, simplifies the two-point correlation function to depend only on the distance between points, not their direction or specific location. This assumption reduces the general form $\xi(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2)$ to $\xi(r) = \langle \delta(\mathbf{x})\delta(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{r}) \rangle$.

In Fourier space, this correlation function transforms into the power spectrum $P(k)$, defined by the Fourier transform

$$P(k) = \int \xi(r) e^{-i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}} d^3r.$$

Here, k represents the wavenumber associated with a particular Fourier mode, and $P(k)$ quantifies the distribution of power among various spatial frequencies of the density fluctuations. This Fourier representation is particularly valuable as it directly links observational data to theoretical models of early universe physics. It describes how fluctuations at different scales contribute to the overall variance observed in the CMB and the large-scale structure of the universe. These fluctuations are thought to originate from quantum fluctuations during the inflationary epoch.

Inversely, the correlation function can be obtained from the power spectrum thanks to an inverse Fourier transform, and for $r = 0$, the variance is recovered according to

$$\sigma^2 = \xi(r = 0) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int P(k) d^3k.$$

However, this integral diverges as k tends towards infinity, that is for increasingly small scales, due to the power spectrum (whose evolution is visible in figure 1) not decreasing fast enough relative to the increasing k^2 . Therefore, in order to avoid this divergence, a filter is usually applied, smoothing the density field and averaging its properties in spheres of a given radius. This is useful to better highlight the large scale structure as it allows to ignore small scale fluctuations. When using such a method, the correlation function is

no longer calculated for two distant points in space but rather two distant spheres of that given radius. The most used filter and the one I used during my work is the top hat filter

$$W_R(r) \equiv \begin{cases} \frac{1}{V(R)}, & \text{if } |r| \leq R \\ 0, & \text{if } |r| > R \end{cases}$$

where $V(R)$ is the volume of the sphere upon which is calculated the correlation function.

2.2 Redshift space

The most direct observable available from surveys is redshift, which combines the effects of galaxies displacements due to both their peculiar velocities and the universe expansion. Recalling that the radial comoving distance can be inferred from the redshift thanks to the relation $r(z) = c \int_0^z dz'/H(z')$, where $H(z) = H_0 \sqrt{\Omega_{m,0}(1+z)^3 + \Omega_{\Lambda,0}}$ and $\Omega_{m,0}$ and $\Omega_{\Lambda,0}$ are the actual density parameters of matter and dark energy respectively (assuming that $\Omega_{m,0} + \Omega_{\Lambda,0} = 1$), shows that the real positions of galaxies determined from redshifts of the survey can vary regarding which cosmology is used (which values of H_0 and $\Omega_{m,0}$). However, several effects are to be taken into account when switching to such a space. Indeed, the density contrast in redshift space would write [4] (the 's' in the exponent denotes that we are in redshift space):

$$\delta_g^s(z, \mathbf{r}) = b(z)\delta_m(z, \mathbf{r}) - \frac{1+z}{H(z)} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} [\mathbf{v}(z, \mathbf{r}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}] - \frac{1+z}{H(z)} \alpha(z) [\mathbf{v}(z, \mathbf{r}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}] + [5s(z) - 2] \kappa(z, \mathbf{r}) + \delta_\Phi(z, \mathbf{r})$$

where each term represents:

- $b(z)$: Linear bias factor, quantifying how galaxy clustering at a redshift z is amplified relative to the clustering of the total mass density (including both dark and baryonic matter).
- $\delta_m(z, \mathbf{r})$: Mass density contrast.
- $\mathbf{v}(z, \mathbf{r})$: Peculiar velocity vector
- $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$: Unit vector along the line-of-sight.
- $\alpha(z)$: Factor that modulates the effect of gravitational redshift, which influences the observed redshift of galaxies as light travels through varying gravitational potentials.
- $\kappa(z, \mathbf{r})$: Convergence in gravitational lensing, reflecting the bending of light by mass along the line-of-sight, which can magnify (make the object look brighter and larger than what it is) or demagnify the images of galaxies and hence affect their observed density (under a certain luminosity level, galaxies become undetectable).
- $s(z)$: Magnification bias, translating the change in the observed number density of galaxies due to the magnification effect.
- $\delta_\Phi(z, \mathbf{r})$: Perturbation in the gravitational potential, which can directly affect the observed redshifts of galaxies due to the gravitational redshift effect.

This first term $b(z)\delta_m(z, \mathbf{r})$ accounts for the bias between the galaxy distribution and the underlying matter distribution. Galaxies do not perfectly trace the total matter distribution. The bias factor $b(z)$ quantifies the relationship between the density contrast of galaxies δ_g^s and the total matter density contrast δ_m . Higher values of $b(z)$ indicate that galaxies are more clustered compared to the matter distribution.

Using redshifts of galaxies to estimate their distances to us leads to shifts in their real positions, as the redshift combines the effects of galaxies displacements due to both the universe expansion and their peculiar velocities. Peculiar velocities, which are proper to each galaxy, cause them to appear displaced along the line-of-sight in the redshift space, distorting the true spatial distribution. This effect, called Kaiser effect or redshift-space distortion (RSD), enhances the clustering signal along the line-of-sight and is taken into account in the redshift space density contrast thanks to the second term $\frac{1+z}{H(z)} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} [\mathbf{v}(z, \mathbf{r}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}]$. It's important to note that due to such distortions, isotropy is no longer valid and therefore not assumed in redshift space. More precisely, considering spherical coordinates system, anisotropy concerns solely the polar angle, while symmetry along the azimuthal one is conserved.

The third term is called Doppler redshift effect and captures the effect of peculiar velocities solely on the redshift.

The fourth term accounts for galaxies density modifications due to gravitational lensing, while the last one takes into consideration effects of gravitational potential variations across different regions of the universe on the traveling photons and therefore their redshifts, called Sachs-Wolf effects.

When studying galaxy clustering, a common practice is to adopt the plane-parallel approximation, where the distance between the two observed objects (the ones for which the correlation function is calculated) is so small in comparison with their distances to the observer that their lines of sight are assumed to be parallel. Therefore, the radial components of their peculiar velocities, which are responsible for RSD, are also assumed to be parallel, allowing for an easier treatment of RSD. This approximation simplifies greatly the calculations involved in determining correlation functions in the redshift space, however, in using such a model, it may not be obvious to detect eventual curvature effects as the distance between the two objects is generally too much smaller than the hypothetical curvature scale. Indeed, for $|\Omega_K|$ smaller than 0.1 which is a safe limit, the curvature scale would be around 5000 Mpc. Hence, it's necessary to move beyond the plane-parallel approximation to be able to survey larger scales and in doing so arise the so-called wide-angle effects. Having two different lines of sight implies observing objects within completely different regions, with different density and gravitational potential fields, and for which the coordinates changes from redshift to real space are different. These are the wide-angle effects.

Also, in real space, the spherical volume element dV_r at a point \mathbf{r} is given by:

$$dV_r = r^2 \sin \theta dr d\theta d\phi,$$

where r is the radial distance from the observer, θ is the polar angle, and ϕ is the azimuthal angle. This volume element tells us the extent a small region occupies in the real space. In redshift space, as already mentionned, peculiar velocities induce changes in the distances and the volume element dV_s is therefore modified with respect to the one in real space. The transformation from real space coordinates \mathbf{r} to redshift space coordinates \mathbf{s} involves a Jacobian determinant that accounts for the stretching or compression of the volume

Figure 2: Diagram representing the observer and the two observed objects. The bending illustrates a hypothetical curvature [9].

element. Mathematically, the volume elements in real and redshift space are related by:

$$dV_s = \left| \frac{\partial(s_1, s_2, s_3)}{\partial(r_1, r_2, r_3)} \right| dV_r,$$

where $\left| \frac{\partial(s_1, s_2, s_3)}{\partial(r_1, r_2, r_3)} \right|$ is the Jacobian determinant of the transformation from real space coordinates (r_1, r_2, r_3) to redshift space coordinates (s_1, s_2, s_3) .

This Jacobian determinant accounts for the fact that peculiar velocities cause galaxies to appear closer together or further apart along the line-of-sight than they actually are. The effect on the volume element leads to changes in the observed number density of galaxies. Specifically, if peculiar velocities cause galaxies to be compressed along the line-of-sight, the observed volume element dV_s is smaller, and thus the number density of galaxies appears higher. Conversely, if galaxies are stretched along the line-of-sight, the volume element dV_s is larger, and the number density appears lower.

The observed galaxy number density $\tilde{n}_g(s)$ in redshift space is related to the real space number density $n_g(r)$ by:

$$\tilde{n}_g(s) = n_g(r) \left| \frac{dV_r}{dV_s} \right|.$$

Here, $\frac{dV_r}{dV_s}$ is the inverse of the Jacobian determinant, indicating how the real space volume element is transformed into the redshift space volume element. Of course, this is to be accounted for in the plane parallel-approximation as well, however the changing lines of sight in the wide-angle version implies a different angle θ , making these volume element and number density changes more important and complex.

2.3 Correlation function with curvature and wide-angle effects

In addition to wide-angle effects, curvature should also be taken into consideration. To this purpose, we rely on the work of [4] and [9] to derive the correlation function as it follows (assuming a FLRW background and based on the diagram in figure 2):

$$\xi_g^s(\chi_1, \chi_2) = b_1 b_2 D_1 D_2 \sum_{n,l} c_l^{(n)}(\chi_1, \chi_2, \theta) \Xi_l^{(n)}(\chi) \quad (2.1)$$

where

$$\Xi_l^{(n)}(\chi) = 4\pi(-1)^n \int d\nu \frac{\nu^2}{(\nu^2 - 4K)^n} S(\nu) X_l^{(K)}(\nu, \chi).$$

$S(\nu)$ is the power spectrum in curved space related to the correlation function in real space as the following

$$S(\nu) = \frac{1}{2\pi^2} \int d^2\Omega d\chi S_K^2(\chi) \xi(\chi) \hat{X}_0^{(K)}(\nu, \chi)$$

$$\text{and } X_l^{(K)}(\nu, \chi) = (-K)^l [S_K(\chi)]^l \frac{d^l X_0^{(K)}(\chi, \nu)}{d[C_K(\chi)]^l}, \quad \text{where } X_0^{(K)}(\nu, \chi) = \frac{\sin(\nu\chi)}{\nu S_K(\chi)}$$

$$\text{with } S_K(\chi) = \begin{cases} \sin \chi & \text{if } K = 1 \\ \chi & \text{if } K = 0 \\ \sinh \chi & \text{if } K = -1 \end{cases} \quad \text{and } C_K(\chi) = \frac{dS_K(\chi)}{d\chi}$$

$\nu^2 = (a_0 k)^2 - K$ is a generalized Fourier wave-number accounting for the curved space effect on the Fourier basis functions which are solutions of the Helmholtz equation instead of being plane waves as in the flat case. a_0 is a scaling factor that relates the comoving radial coordinate χ to the comoving effective distance r ($r = a_0\chi$) and thus accounts for the curvature bending the distances. It's therefore defined as

$$a_0 = \frac{c}{H_0} \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } K = 0 \\ |\Omega_{K,0}|^{-1/2} & \text{if } K \neq 0 \end{cases}$$

Also $b_i = b(z_i)$ is the linear bias factor and $D_i = D(z_i) = \delta_m(z_i, \chi)/\delta_m(0, \chi)$ is the growth factor measuring how much density perturbations have grown from an earlier time (characterized by a higher redshift) to the present day. Finally, the coefficients $c_l^{(n)}$ are obtained from the so-called redshift distortion operators which relate the overdensity field in the real space to the one in the redshift space.

Let us delve into the flat scenario as the Euclid mock catalogues under study represent a flat space. In such a case, the only non-vanishing coefficients are [11]

$$c_0^{(0)} = 1 + \frac{1}{3}(\beta_1 + \beta_2) + \frac{1}{15}\beta_1\beta_2 (1 + 2 \cos^2 \vartheta), \quad (2.2)$$

$$c_2^{(1)} = \frac{\beta_1}{3} (3 \cos^2 \gamma_1 - 1) + \frac{\beta_2}{3} (3 \cos^2 \gamma_2 - 1) - \frac{\beta_1\beta_2}{21} [2 + 4 \cos^2 \vartheta - 3 (\cos^2 \gamma_1 + \cos^2 \gamma_2) + 12 \cos \gamma_1 \cos \gamma_2 \cos \vartheta],$$

$$c_4^{(2)} = \frac{\beta_1\beta_2}{35} [1 + 2 \cos^2 \vartheta - 5 (\cos^2 \gamma_1 + \cos^2 \gamma_2) + 20 \cos \gamma_1 \cos \gamma_2 \cos \vartheta + 35 \cos^2 \gamma_1 \cos^2 \gamma_2]$$

with $\beta_i = f_i/b_i$ and $f = -\partial \ln D / \partial \ln(1+z) = \partial \ln D / \partial \ln(a)$ is the growth rate, describing how fast density perturbations grow in the universe. The angle ϑ is expressed as [4]

$$\cos \vartheta = \frac{C_1 C_2 \cos \theta + K S_1 S_2}{C_1 C_2 + K S_1 S_2 \cos \theta},$$

where $C_i = C_K(\chi_i)$, $S_i = S_K(\chi_i)$ and C_i and S_i are related by $C_i^2 + K S_i^2 = 1$. In the flat case, $K = 0$ and $C_K(\chi_i) = 1$, allowing to have $\vartheta = \theta$.

Besides, in redshift space, the correlation function can also be decomposed into a series of multipoles times Legendre polynomials L_ℓ to separate it into a isotropic part (multipoles) and an anisotropic one (Legendre polynomials) and thus to simplify its analysis:

$$\xi_g^s(\chi, \mu) = \sum_{\ell} \xi^{(\ell)}(\chi) L_{\ell}(\mu), \quad \text{with } \mu = \cos \gamma_1. \quad (2.3)$$

Let us try to write the coefficients (2.2) in terms of Legendre polynomials to infer the correlation function multipoles. Regarding figure 2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_1 \cdot \chi &= -\chi_1 \chi \cos(\gamma_1), \\ \chi_2 \cdot \chi &= \chi_2 \chi \cos \gamma_2, \\ \chi_2 &= \chi_1 + \chi. \end{aligned}$$

From these relations, it can be easily shown that

$$\cos \gamma_2 = \frac{\chi - \chi_1 \cos \gamma_1}{\sqrt{\chi_1^2 + \chi^2 - 2\chi_1 \chi \cos(\gamma_1)}}$$

It's fair, and it's going to be obvious in the next chapters when the distances orders of magnitude will be stated and discussed, to assume the small angles limit, where the distances χ_1 and χ_2 are much bigger than χ . This limit doesn't imply that we are neglecting wide angle effects and taking the plane-parallel approximation. This being said, we can use a small parameter $\epsilon = \chi/\chi_1$ to get rid of the χ and χ_1 terms. Then, expanding the denominator in Taylor series up to the first order in ϵ , we are left with

$$\cos \gamma_2 \approx \epsilon(1 - \cos^2 \gamma_1) - \cos \gamma_1$$

Similarly, it can be shown that $\cos(\theta) \approx 1$ which makes sense knowing that we are in the small angles limit.

Now the coefficients (2.2) can be expressed in terms of $\cos(\gamma_1)$ and ϵ only, and to make appear Legendre polynomials in their expressions, we remind the following [11]

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &= L_0, \\ \cos \gamma_1 &= L_1, \\ \cos^2 \gamma_1 &= \frac{2}{3}L_2 + \frac{1}{3}L_0, \\ \cos^3 \gamma_1 &= \frac{2}{5}L_3 + \frac{3}{5}L_1, \\ \cos^4 \gamma_1 &= \frac{8}{35}L_4 + \frac{4}{7}L_2 + \frac{1}{5}L_0, \\ \cos^5 \gamma_1 &= \frac{8}{63}L_5 + \frac{4}{9}L_3 + \frac{3}{7}L_1. \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

Thanks to (2.4), we finally get

$$\begin{aligned} c_0^{(0)} &= \left(1 + \frac{2}{3}\beta + \frac{1}{5}\beta^2\right)L_0, \\ c_2^{(1)} &= \frac{4}{3}\beta \left[L_2 + \frac{3}{5}\epsilon(L_3 - L_1) \right] + \frac{4}{7}\beta^2 \left[L_2 + \frac{3}{5}\epsilon(L_3 - L_1) \right], \\ c_4^{(2)} &= \frac{8}{35}\beta^2 \left[L_4 + \frac{10}{9}\epsilon(L_5 - L_3) \right], \end{aligned}$$

so that the first three multipoles are

$$\begin{aligned}\xi_s^{(0)} &= b^2 D^2 \left(1 + \frac{2\beta}{3} + \frac{\beta^2}{5} \right) \Xi_0^{(0)}, \\ \xi_s^{(1)} &= b^2 D^2 \frac{3}{5} \epsilon \left(\frac{4\beta}{3} + \frac{4\beta^2}{7} \right) \Xi_2^{(1)}, \\ \xi_s^{(2)} &= b^2 D^2 \left(\frac{4\beta}{3} + \frac{4\beta^2}{7} \right) \Xi_2^{(1)},\end{aligned}\tag{2.5}$$

where we considered that the quantities b_i and D_i are the same for the two observed objects. This result already highlights the impact of wide-angle effects. Indeed, in plane-parallel approximation, further simplifications would have implied vanishing multipoles [9].

In my work, I exploited this feature of the beyond plane-parallel model where odd multipoles aren't vanishing. In particular, I studied the evolution of the ratio between the dipole and the quadrupole as a function of the separation χ between the two observed objects. From results (2.5), in a flat universe, such a ratio would be $\xi^{(1)}/\xi^{(2)} = 3\chi/5\chi_1$. The catalogues I worked on assume a flat space. My objective was to verify if the theoretical ratio is accurately retrieved when analyzing the data and to determine the conditions under which it is properly detectable. This is crucial to assess if the forthcoming Euclid data will be sufficient to detect the ratio and, hence, any potential deviations from its expected evolution in a flat universe. Such deviations would indicate the presence of curvature and provide insights into the value of $\Omega_{K,0}$.

3 Euclid mock data

Let us delve into how the Euclid mock data I used are generated. The generation of such data is essentially split into two parts, a first one consisting in generating empty dark matter halos in a distribution similar to the one we observe today, while the second one aims at filling these halos with galaxies.

The first step is completed thanks to the PINOCCHIO algorithm [10]. Indeed, the PINpointing Orbit-Crossing Collapsed Hierarchical Objects (PINOCCHIO) method offers an efficient way to create dark matter halo catalogs. Unlike traditional N-body simulations that require significant computational resources, PINOCCHIO utilizes a semi-analytic approach that allows for the rapid generation of halo catalogs while maintaining high accuracy. The core of the PINOCCHIO method is based on Lagrangian perturbation theory, which provides a framework for predicting the evolution of initial density perturbations into collapsed structures. The process begins with the generation of a linear over-density field (of dark matter), $\delta(\mathbf{x})$, based on theoretical models of inflation predicting Gaussian, nearly scale-invariant perturbations, sampled on a regular grid. Then, this field is smoothed thanks to a filter of the same type as the one mentioned in the previous chapter. Particularly, the smoothing is operated for different values of the filter radius to capture structures of different sizes. The over-dense structures are identified, and, as they are the likelier to collapse, their collapse time is calculated. To do so, PINOCCHIO employs ellipsoidal collapse models rather than spherical ones, which are more accurate in describing the actual dynamics of structure formation, as structures in the universe are not perfectly spherical, they are more complex, often elongated or flattened, influenced by anisotropic forces and surrounding density fields. The key idea is to calculate the collapse

time by considering the deformation tensor, which characterizes the tidal forces acting on a given region, the latter are indeed determining in the collapse mechanism.

The collapse time, t_c , is obtained by solving the equation [5]

$$1 - \lambda_1 t_c - \frac{3}{14} \lambda_1 (\delta - \lambda_1) t_c^2 - \left(\frac{\mu_3}{126} + \frac{5}{84} \lambda_1 \delta (\delta - \lambda_1) \right) t_c^3 = 0,$$

where $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ are the eigenvalues of the deformation tensor, δ is the initial over-density and $\mu_3 = \lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3$. Once the collapse times are determined, PINOCCHIO groups the collapsed regions into halos. This is done hierarchically, starting with small scales (e.g., small halos) and moving to larger ones (e.g., galaxy clusters).

To ensure that the halo catalogue generated by PINOCCHIO is consistent with observational and simulation data, a recalibration process is applied. Initially, the masses of PINOCCHIO halos are recalibrated to achieve abundance matching with halo masses obtained from Flagship, a state-of-the-art cosmological N-body simulation used by the Euclid mission, providing a detailed and accurate representation of halo properties and clustering but computationally expensive (PINOCCHIO is at least 1000 times faster than N-body simulations). This step ensures that the overall number density of halos matches between the two catalogues. However, despite this initial recalibration, PINOCCHIO halos do not cluster exactly as Flagship halos. To address this discrepancy, a second recalibration of the halo masses is performed, which is done by adjusting the halo masses. Therefore, the spatial distribution and large-scale clustering properties of the PINOCCHIO halos are brought into better agreement with the high-fidelity simulations of the Flagship project. In this way, a realistic dark matter halo catalog is created.

After generating dark matter halo catalogs with the PINOCCHIO method, the next critical step in creating mock galaxy catalogs is to populate these halos with galaxies using the Halo Occupation Distribution (HOD) model. The HOD provides a statistical framework that describes how galaxies are distributed within dark matter halos, based on halo properties such as mass. This approach is essential for connecting the theoretical models of dark matter structures with observable galaxies.

The HOD model specifies the probability distribution $P(N|M)$, where N represents the number of galaxies within a halo of mass M . This distribution is typically divided into contributions from central and satellite galaxies. The number of central galaxies in a halo is modeled as a Bernoulli distribution with a mean occupancy $\langle N_{\text{cen}} \rangle$, given by [15]:

$$\langle N_{\text{cen}} \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \text{erf} \left(\frac{\log M - \log M_{\text{min}}}{\sigma_{\log M}} \right) \right],$$

where M_{min} is the minimum halo mass for hosting a central galaxy, and $\sigma_{\log M}$ accounts for the characteristic transition width, quantifying the range of halo masses over which the probability of hosting a central galaxy increases from zero to unity. The error function, $\text{erf}(x)$, is defined as:

$$\text{erf}(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x e^{-t^2} dt.$$

For satellite galaxies, the number follows a Poisson distribution with a mean occupancy $\langle N_{\text{sat}} \rangle$, conditional on the presence of a central galaxy [15]:

$$\langle N_{\text{sat}} \rangle = \left(\frac{M_h - M_0}{M_1} \right)^\alpha,$$

where M_0 is the cutoff mass below which halos do not host satellite galaxies, M_1 is the mass at which one satellite galaxy is expected on average, and α is an index that depends on the theory used to model the galaxy distribution and is usually close to 1.

The spatial distribution of galaxies within halos is another key component of the HOD model. Central galaxies are usually placed at the center of the dark matter halo, while satellite galaxies are distributed according to the dark matter density profile of the halo, often modeled by the Navarro-Frenk-White (NFW) profile [14]:

$$\rho(r) = \frac{\rho_0}{(r/r_s)(1+r/r_s)^2},$$

where r is the radial distance from the halo center, r_s is a scale radius at which the logarithmic slope of the density profile changes, and ρ_0 is a normalization constant. The positions of satellite galaxies are sampled according to this profile.

Once again, the Flagship simulation is used as a reference. Indeed, the mean number of central and satellite galaxies is measured from the Flagship simulation and then used to assign galaxies to the recalibrated PINOCCHIO halos.

Finally, observational systematics, such as redshift measurement errors and selection effects, are incorporated into the data obtained to mimic real survey conditions and the sky as it would be observed by Euclid.

I conducted my study using 1000 Euclid mock catalogues, all generated using the same method described above. Using such a large number of catalogues has several advantages, including reducing variances and errors, which leads to more precise measurements. Also, as the whole work was conducted on a flat space, therefore, throughout the report, χ_i will refer to the physical distance (normally r), as r and χ are related by a constant (c/H_0) that we will somehow set equal to 1.

These catalogues are divided into four bins based on minimum and maximum radial distances to the observer, χ_1 , as follows:

$$\text{bin 1: } \chi_1 \in [2113.9923; 2447.2738]h^{-1}Mpc \Leftrightarrow z \in [0.9; 1.1]$$

$$\text{bin 2: } \chi_1 \in [2447.2738; 2743.9894]h^{-1}Mpc \Leftrightarrow z \in [1.1; 1.3]$$

$$\text{bin 3: } \chi_1 \in [2743.9894; 3009.5035]h^{-1}Mpc \Leftrightarrow z \in [1.3; 1.5]$$

$$\text{bin 4: } \chi_1 \in [3009.5035; 3359.0501]h^{-1}Mpc \Leftrightarrow z \in [1.5; 1.7]$$

This division is designed to create bins large enough to survey the BAO scale ($\approx 150Mpc$) with sufficient precision while maximizing the number of bins.

4 Algorithm building and first tests

The correlation function can be calculated for two distant points or objects. For a whole catalogue of astronomical objects, it can be evaluated for each pair of objects in order to infer an average value. These objects are spheres of the order of 10 Mpc as the over-density field should be smoothed thanks to a top-hat filter of the same radius.

I had therefore to superpose on the survey, which is a cone of semi angle equal to 30° filled with points representing galaxies, another cone having exactly the same geometry but filled with spheres of radius R (from now on, R is the filter radius), to count how many points fall into the spheres. To do so, the cone has been split into layers, spaced between each others by a distance equal to R . Each layer is a circle of radius $\lambda = z \tan(\alpha)$ where z is the height equal to the rank of the layer multiplied by R and α is the cone semi

angle, and within each of those circles are drawn sub-circles of radii $\rho = \lambda - nR$, where n is an integer going from 1 until its highest value for which ρ is still strictly positive. Then, on each of those sub-circles will be placed the spheres (figure 4), and specifically their centers, by assigning to them cylindrical coordinates. The third coordinate, the height, is simply the one of the layer, z . The first one, the radius, is the radius of the sub-circle on which the sphere is located, ρ . To assign the second coordinate, the azimuthal angle φ , it's determined first the number of spheres that will be put on the given sub-circle. The latter is m , the integer part of $2\pi\rho/(0.7 \times 2R)$, which is the sub-circle circumference divided by the sphere diameter. The denominator is multiplied by a factor 0.7 to allow for an overlapping of the spheres of the same sub-circle. By the way, the spacing between the layers and the sub-circles within a same layer have also been chosen in a way to allow for a significant overlapping. This has been done in the interest of surveying as much volume as possible thanks to the spheres, while it has been shown that the overlapping, until a certain point which hasn't been reached here, doesn't affect the correlation results [3]. The azimuthal coordinate for each sphere is $\varphi = i2\pi/m$, i is an integer ranging from 0 to $m - 1$, uniquely identifying each of the m spheres on the sub-circle. The cylindrical coordinates are finally converted into cartesian ones.

The counting is performed by calculating the distance between a galaxy position (given in Cartesian coordinates in the mock catalogues) and the center of a sphere and by checking if this distance is smaller than R , in which case the galaxy would be counted as belonging to the sphere. Nevertheless, doing such an operation for all the points, and then repeating it for all the spheres, implies a huge computational load, recalling that a catalogue contains over 40 Million galaxies, that the cone contains, for $R = 18h^{-1}Mpc$ and a cone height of about $4000h^{-1}Mpc$, over 1 Million spheres and that there are 1000 mock catalogues to study. Therefore, one of the issues I had to deal with was to conceive an algorithm that performs the counting extremely fast. To respond to this problematic, the coordinates (of both galaxies and sphere centers) have been discretized to place galaxies and spheres on a 3 dimensional cubic grid with a spacing equal to $l = 1.1R$. This was done by taking each of the 3 coordinates and dividing it by l , if the result is bigger than $j.5$, than the resulting new coordinate is $j + 1$, if not then it's j . From the coordinates (x, y, z) are therefore obtained the discrete coordinates (i, j, k) . Then the points (galaxies) are organised into a data structure, 'unorderedmap' in C++ [6], where for each unique combination of the values i, j and k is assigned a unique index that allows to identify the point within the structure. If multiple points have the same (i, j, k) , they are stored in a vector associated with those coordinates and identified with a given index. After this, for each sphere with a given (i', j', k') , a corresponding index is calculated using the same method as for the points, and also the indices corresponding to the coordinates falling in the ranges $([i' - 1, i' + 1], [j' - 1, j' + 1], [k' - 1, k' + 1])$. This gives a total of 27 indices, thanks to which the points with coordinates (i, j, k) falling in this same range will be retrieved directly in the structure. For those points only, a calculation of the distance between their position and that of the sphere, based on the original coordinates (x, y, z) , is performed to check if they are within the sphere or not. This method saves a tremendous amount of time while ensuring that all the points potentially in the sphere are taken into account. To this purpose, the spacing l should be necessarily bigger than R .

Figure 3: Cone split into layers

Figure 4: Layer as viewed from above. The spheres are being placed along the sub-circles drawn in dashed lines.

Figure 5: Probability distribution function in random catalogues, for spheres of radius $R = 18h^{-1}Mpc$.

4.1 Probability distribution function of a random catalogue

After having put the spheres all through the survey cone, a first test of the counting correctness can be made using catalogues generated randomly. Indeed, the likelihood of finding a certain number of points within a sphere, that is the probability distribution function (PDF), for a random spatial distribution of points, should follow a Poisson distribution as it's a stochastic process. The random catalogue is built first by setting a total number of points, which has been chosen arbitrarily. Next, for each point, a set of three random numbers is generated, representing the Cartesian coordinates (x, y, z) of the point, with the values restricted to a specified range. This results in a cube of points. Then, a counting of the number of points in each sphere is made, thanks to which is inferred the PDF in figure 5, averaged over 10 different catalogues generated randomly. It's indeed the expected Poisson distribution, allowing therefore to move safely to the next step, the correlation function.

4.2 Correlation function of a random catalogue

As already mentioned, the correlation function is measured for each pair of spheres. To define these pairs, we follow the procedure outlined in [3]. Specifically, for each sphere within the cone, referred to as the seed, a set of spheres is distributed isotropically around it. These spheres, that describe a precise motif, are placed at a distance χ from the seed, which corresponds to the scale at which the correlation function will be calculated. In particular, the multipoles of the latter are of interest. From the expression (2.3), one can make the following development (reminding that $\mu = \cos(\gamma)$):

$$\begin{aligned}\xi_g^s(\chi, \mu) &= \sum_{\ell} \xi^{(\ell)}(\chi) L_{\ell}(\mu) \\ \Leftrightarrow \int_{-1}^1 L_{\ell'} \xi_g^s(\chi, \mu) d\mu &= \int_{-1}^1 L_{\ell'} \sum_{\ell} \xi^{(\ell)}(\chi) L_{\ell}(\mu) d\mu\end{aligned}$$

Using the orthogonality relation of Legendre polynomials

$$\int_{-1}^1 L_{\ell'} L_{\ell}(\mu) d\mu = \frac{2}{2\ell + 1} \delta_{\ell' \ell},$$

we infer

$$\int_{-1}^1 L_{\ell'} \xi_g^s(\chi, \mu) d\mu = \frac{2}{2\ell' + 1} \sum_{\ell'} \xi^{(\ell')}(\chi),$$

where ℓ' is now a fixed unique value of ℓ , so there is nothing to sum over, such as we are left with

$$\xi^{(\ell')}(\chi) = \frac{1}{2}(2\ell' + 1) \int_{-1}^1 L_{\ell'}(\mu) \xi_g^s(\chi, \mu) d\mu.$$

This is the formula to obtain the multipole of order ℓ' from its correlation function and it's valid in the real space as well. Also, the right hand-side integral above can be easily determined using the Gauss-Legendre quadrature [1], allowing to infer an even more convenient expression for the monopoles:

$$\xi^{(\ell')}(\chi) = \frac{1}{2}(2\ell' + 1) \sum_i^n \omega_i L_{\ell'}(\mu_i) \xi_g^s(\chi, \mu_i), \quad (4.1)$$

with ω_i the quadrature weights and μ_i the values of μ in the range $[-1, 1]$ corresponding to the roots of the n th Legendre polynomial and related to those weights. There is therefore no need to measure the correlation function for the whole range $[-1, 1]$ of μ values, but rather only for a set of these values and hence, the motif spheres around the seeds can be placed dependently. The choice of the number of points, $n = 5$, has been made regarding observations of the evolution of the correlation function with respect to μ , to maximise accuracy while minimising computational cost due to an excessive number of spheres. For $n = 5$, the roots and related weights are the following:

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_0 &= 0.0000000000000000 & \omega_0 &= 0.5688888888888889 \\ \mu_{\pm 1} &= \pm 0.538469310105683 & \omega_1 &= 0.478628670499366 \\ \mu_{\pm 2} &= \pm 0.906179845938664 & \omega_2 &= 0.236926885056189\end{aligned}$$

Thus, the motif spheres around the seeds are positioned at $\gamma_{1i} = \arccos(\mu_i)$, where γ_{1i} is the angle between the line-of-sight to the seed and the separation between the seed and the motif sphere. For each value of γ_{1i} , which represents the polar angle in the spherical coordinate system centered at the seed, motif spheres are distributed along the circle formed by a full 360° rotation of the azimuthal angle. The number of motif

Figure 6: Diagram of the motif made of the blue spheres around the red one, the seed, for the three first polar angles γ_{1i} . We omitted to make the motif spheres overlap for a better visibility. The angle between the first black axis, representing χ_1 , and the second one linking the seed to the motif sphere is the polar angle γ_{11} .

spheres placed on this circle is determined similarly to the seeds, given by m' , the integer part of $2\pi\chi \sin(\gamma_{1i}) / (0.7 \times 2R)$, where $2\pi\chi \sin(\gamma_{1i})$ is the circumference of the circle, $2R$ is the diameter of the motif spheres, and the factor 0.7 allows for overlapping. In the spherical coordinate system centered at the seed, the motif spheres have coordinates $(\chi, \gamma_{1i}, j2\pi/m')$, where j is an integer ranging from 0 to $m' - 1$, uniquely identifying each of the m' spheres on the circle. Figure 6 illustrates this positioning.

Then, these spherical coordinates are converted into Cartesian ones (x'', y'', z'') with respect to the frame R'' centered at the seed, which has a rotation of the polar angle θ and azimuthal angle φ , the spherical coordinates of the seed, with respect to the frame R centered at the cone vertex as shown in figure 7. Thus a rotation matrix should be applied to convert these Cartesian coordinates (x'', y'', z'') into the frame centered at the seed but aligned (without any rotation) with the global frame. In such a frame, the motif spheres would have coordinates (x', y', z') :

$$\begin{pmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\varphi) \cos(\theta) & -\sin(\varphi) & \cos(\varphi) \sin(\theta) \\ \sin(\varphi) \cos(\theta) & \cos(\varphi) & \sin(\varphi) \sin(\theta) \\ -\sin(\theta) & 0 & \cos(\theta) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x'' \\ y'' \\ z'' \end{pmatrix}$$

Finally, coordinates (x', y', z') are converted into the global frame centered at the cone vertex simply by adding them to the seed Cartesian coordinates in this same frame.

Now everything is set up to measure the correlation function. As mentioned at the beginning of this chapter, an average can be calculated for the whole catalogue. The latter can be evaluated thanks to the formula [3] (valid in real space as well):

$$\xi_g^s(\chi, \mu_i) = \frac{1}{n_s n_{\text{mot}}(\mu_i)} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^{n_s} \delta_{N,i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{\text{mot}}} \delta_{N,ij} \right\}, \quad \text{where} \quad \delta_N = \frac{N}{\bar{N}} - 1.$$

Here \bar{N} is the expected number of galaxies within a sphere (based on the density of the catalogue) and N is the effective number of galaxies within the sphere as determined by

Figure 7: Diagram of the frame R'' with respect to the frame R (the main one). The origin of R is the cone vertex and the observer position.

the counting, such as $\delta_{N,i}$ is the density contrast (or overdensity) of the seed i and $\delta_{N,ij}(\mu_i)$ is the density contrast of the motif sphere j of the same seed for a given μ_i . n_s is the total number of seeds while $n_{\text{mot}}(\mu_i)$ is the number of spheres in the motif for a given (μ_i) . The product $n_s n_{\text{mot}}(\mu_i)$ aims at taking into account all the motif spheres upon which the counting has been operated to infer the average, however, not all of them participates effectively in this counting. In fact, only motif spheres with their whole volume inside the cone are considered in the counting, hence, the product $n_s n_{\text{mot}}(\mu_i)$ should be multiplied by a probability factor $p(\mu_i)$ that takes into account the motif spheres outside the cone and which is determined for each different combination of μ_i , χ and R .

We start with a verification of the process by measuring the correlation functions of 4 different catalogues generated randomly. In such a case, there is no clustering at a given scale or any phenomenon that can justify a correlation in matter distribution over a given scale, thus, we should expect extremely small values, negative and positive, fluctuating around zero. Also, as we are not in redshift space, isotropy is expected and hence there should be no dependence upon μ_i at least when taking into account the probability factor $p(\mu_i)$ correction. Thus, only small fluctuations from a value of μ_i to another one should be tolerated.

On figure 8, one can see that taking into account the probabilistic correction by dividing the results by $p(\mu_i) = [0.77, 0.85, 0.91, 0.84, 0.76]$ (from the smaller to the bigger value of μ_i respectively) doesn't have a significant effect. Both the plots show that the results match the expectations of having small values fluctuating around 0 and no dependence over μ_i , demonstrating the efficiency of the algorithm so far.

Figure 8: Correlation function, for $\chi = 72h^{-1}Mpc$ and $R = 18h^{-1}Mpc$, in random catalogues before (left) and after (right) probabilistic correction.

5 Results and discussion

5.1 Correlation function in real space

The galaxies Cartesian coordinates in real space are directly provided in the mock catalogues, but the densities of those catalogues are to be determined. We observe further and further in the past as radial distance of galaxies to us increases. In the past, galaxies were fewer, thus the density is expected to evolve with the radial distance, this is why we reevaluate the density every $2.405h^{-1}Mpc$. This value comes from the fact that we wanted to divide the volume into 1600 bins, but different values wouldn't impact significantly the results, as long as the bins aren't too large and hence the changing densities effects aren't captured anymore. A continuous evolution of the density with the radial distance χ_1 is then obtained by interpolating linearly between the density values evaluated. Thus, for each seed or motif sphere, the expected number of galaxies \bar{N} is calculated based on the radial distance of the sphere. To rapidly retrieve the right values of the density between which the linear interpolation should be operated to find the exact density for the sphere, a method similar to the one that has been used to retrieve the points in the vicinity of a sphere is applied. This being said, in figure 9 are shown the results of the measure of the correlation function averaged over the 1000 mock catalogues for the first bin ($\chi_1 \in [2113.9923, 2447.2738] h^{-1}Mpc$), $\chi = 72h^{-1}Mpc$ and $R = 18h^{-1}Mpc$. One can see that the correction diminishes the fluctuations from a value of μ_i to another one, which is the desired effect. Then, the shape of the correlation function can seem to be quite regular, but this is only due to the averaging, the shapes for individual catalogues were completely irregular and changing from a catalogue to another without any preferred motif. Further verification of the results is recommended to ensure their reliability. To this end, I used the power spectrum provided with the catalogues (its values are averaged over the 1000 catalogues) to infer the monopole of the correlation function in order to compare it with the monopole inferred from the correlation function results in figure 9. The monopole can be obtained from the power spectrum using the formula [3]

$$\xi^0(\chi) = \int P(k) \hat{W}^2(kR) j_0(k\chi) d^3k,$$

where $\hat{W}_R^2(kR) = 3j_1(kR)/(kR)$ is the Fourier transform of the top-hat filter and j_n is the spherical Bessel function of order n . The values of the power spectrum were given only

Figure 9: Correlation function in real space, in the first bin for $\chi = 72h^{-1}Mpc$, $R = 18h^{-1}Mpc$ and averaged over the 1000 Euclid mock catalogues.

for $k \in [10^{-4}, 10]$ regularly in $\ln(k)$, meaning that $\ln(k_{i+1}) - \ln(k_i)$ is constant. Thus, an interpolation and extrapolation from the values available was necessary to infer the continuous evolution of $P(k)$ and to calculate the monopole. The result of this a process is shown in figure 10, and the monopole evolution with χ in figure 11. For $\chi = 72h^{-1}Mpc$, $\xi^0 \approx 0.00208129$ as inferred from the power spectrum. Now using the formula (4.1) and the results highlighted in figure 9, we find $\xi^0(\chi = 72) \approx 0.0020322$. The two results match therefore greatly.

Figure 10: Power spectrum of the Euclid mock catalogues

Figure 11: Monopole evolution with χ for $R = 18h^{-1}Mpc$, as inferred from the power spectrum

5.2 Correlation function in redshift space

The coordinates provided with the catalogues are those related to the real space as mentioned, and to move to the redshift space, one has to convert them using the total redshifts of the galaxies, i.e. the ones taking into account both the peculiar velocities and the universe expansion. The difference between redshift and real space lies in the radial distance of objects to the observer as the additional component in redshift space is the radial component of peculiar velocities, therefore, considering a spherical coordinate system, the polar and azimuthal angles coordinates are conserved when switching from a space to another one. Thus, we first convert the real space Cartesian coordinates into spherical ones to obtain two of the three coordinates in redshift space. The missing coordinate, the radial one, is obtained from the total redshift (including universe expansion and peculiar velocities) as provided with the catalogues, thanks to the relation $\chi(z) = \int_0^z dz'/H(z')$ and using a cosmology defined by the parameters $H_0 = 67km.s^{-1}.Mpc^{-1}$ and $\Omega_{m,0} = 0.32$. Figure 12 displays the correlation function in redshift space for the first bin and for 4 different values of χ , and now we can see an obvious dependance over μ_i as it's expected in redshift space. The bell shape with a peak at $\mu = 0$, that is along the line-of-sight, can be attributed to the kaiser effect explained in chapter 2. The validity of these results can be further tested using the fact that the ratio between the monopole in redshift space and the one in real space remains constant regardless of the value of χ . Indeed, from (2.5), the monopole in redshift space is

$$\xi_s^{(0)} = b^2 D^2 \left(1 + \frac{2\beta}{3} + \frac{\beta^2}{5} \right) \Xi_0^{(0)}.$$

The monopole in real space can be easily inferred by simply killing the peculiar velocities in the expression above. The continuity equation, which ensures mass conservation in the context of a dynamic universe, writes

$$\frac{\partial \delta_m}{\partial \eta} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v},$$

Figure 12: Correlation function in redshift space, in the first bin, for $R = 18h^{-1}Mpc$ and averaged over the 1000 Euclid mock catalogues. The error bars are too small to be visible.

where δ_m is the mass over-density field, η the conformal time and \mathbf{v} the peculiar velocity field. Reminding that $D(z) = \delta_m(z, \chi)/\delta_m(0, \chi)$ (chapter 2), it's inferred that $\partial\delta_m/\delta_m = \partial D/D$, allowing to rewrite the left hand side of the continuity equation as $D'\delta_m/D$, where the prime denotes the partial derivative with respect to (w.r.t) conformal time. Then, applying a derivative w.r.t time to $f = \partial \ln D / \partial \ln(a)$, we obtain $Hf = (\ln(D))'/a$, thus $D'/D = aHf$, and the continuity equation becomes

$$aHf\delta_m = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}.$$

Switching to Fourier space, ∇ is replaced by $i\mathbf{k}$, and multiplying both side of the equation by $-i\mathbf{k}$, we finally obtain the peculiar velocity field

$$\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{i\mathbf{k}}{k^2} aHf\delta_m(\mathbf{k})$$

Therefore, killing the peculiar velocities is equivalent to killing the growth rate f and hence $\beta = f/b$. The real space monopole is $\xi_s^{(0)} = b^2 D^2 \Xi_0^{(0)}$ and the ratio is indeed independant on χ :

$$\frac{\xi_s^{(0)}}{\xi_r^{(0)}} = 1 + \frac{2\beta}{3} + \frac{\beta^2}{5}.$$

For $b = 1.4$ and $f = 1$, the ratio is approximately 1.58 which is in agreement with the ratios found empirically. Now we can move to the next and main step of this study, the ratio dipole - quadrupole in redshift space and its detectability.

5.3 Dipole-to-quadrupole ratio

As demonstrated in chapter 2, $\xi^{(1)}/\xi^{(2)}$ is expected to evolve as $3\chi/5\chi_1$ in a flat universe. As the correlation function that allows to infer the multipoles is obtained by averaging

the correlation functions over all the spheres in the concerned bin, we take χ_1 as the radial distance corresponding to the mean redshift corresponding to the bin. For the first bin defined by $z \in [0.9; 1.1]$, this corresponds to $\chi_1(\bar{z} = 1) = 2285.9h^{-1}Mpc$. Figure 13 shows that the expected evolution is well retrieved, matching the flatness of the catalogues. However, this good match between the empirical and theoretical evolutions isn't that obvious for higher scales as it can be seen from the last two points. This could be attributed to the approximation that has been made in order to determine the theoretical ratio, that is $\epsilon = \chi/\chi_1$ should be small. Therefore this approximation must not be valid from around $70 h^{-1}Mpc$ according to figure 13. The error bars being bigger at these two points may also explain the deviation.

Figure 13: Evolution of the ratio $R = \xi^{(1)}/\xi^{(2)}$ multiplied by $5\chi_1(z = 1)/3$ w.r.t χ . SEM stands for standard error of the mean.

The standard errors of the mean (SEM) have been obtained by taking the square roots of the variances over the number of observations N , that is 1000. Furthermore, N can be adjusted to estimate the SEM for another number of observations. What's interesting is to determine from how many observations the SEM become smaller than the corresponding ratios, meaning therefore that those ratios are detectable. In fact, each observation can be seen as representing a distinct volume surveyed by Euclid. By determining the number of observations required to ensure proper detectability of the ratio, we can ascertain how many times larger the surveyed volume must be compared to the actual volume of the observations (i.e., the catalogues, which correspond to the volume surveyed by Euclid at its first data release) to detect the ratio. Figure 13 shows that the ratio becomes detectable from 2 observations for moderate values of χ , hence a volume at least twice bigger than actual one surveyed is necessary, which will be reached by 2027 normally. By then, eventual deviations from flatness regime ratios can be looked for to gain insights into a potential curvature. Talking about curvature, it's interesting to give a glimpse of the evolution of the ratio in a curved space. To this purpose, let's give the full set of $c_l^{(n)}$

coefficients in correlation function expression (2.1) in presence of curvature:

$$\begin{aligned}
c_0^{(0)} &= 1 + \frac{2}{3}\beta + \frac{1}{15}\beta^2 (1 + 2 \cos^2 \vartheta) , \\
c_0^{(1)} &= \left[2\beta + \frac{2}{15}\beta^2 (4 + 3 \cos \vartheta) \right] |K| , \\
c_2^{(1)} &= \frac{2\beta}{3} (3 \cos^2 \gamma_1 - 1) \\
&\quad - \frac{\beta^2}{21} [2 + 4 \cos^2 \vartheta - 3 (\cos^2 \gamma_1 + \cos^2 \gamma_2) + 12 \cos \gamma_1 \cos \gamma_2 \cos \vartheta] , \\
c_0^{(2)} &= \beta |K| , \\
c_2^{(2)} &= \frac{\beta^2}{21} [6 \cos^2 \vartheta - 4 + 27 (\cos^2 \gamma_1 + \cos^2 \gamma_2) + 60 \cos \gamma_1 \cos \gamma_2 \cos \vartheta] |K| , \\
c_4^{(2)} &= \frac{\beta^2}{35} [1 + 2 \cos^2 \vartheta - 5 (\cos^2 \gamma_1 + \cos^2 \gamma_2) + 20 \cos \gamma_1 \cos \gamma_2 \cos \vartheta + 35 \cos^2 \gamma_1 \cos^2 \gamma_2] .
\end{aligned}$$

In a curved space, χ , χ_1 , χ_2 and θ are related through the relation [9]

$$C = C_1 C_2 + K S_1 S_2 \cos \theta .$$

By taking the partial derivatives of this relation w.r.t χ_1 and χ_2 we obtain

$$C_1 = C C_2 + K S S_2 \cos \gamma_2$$

$$C_2 = C C_1 + K S S_1 \cos \gamma_1 .$$

From this system of equations we can easily infer that

$$\cos(\theta) = \frac{C S_1 - C_1 S \cos \gamma_1}{S_2} ,$$

and from this same system and the relation $C_2 + K S_2 = 1$, we can express S_2 without C_2 , such as

$$S_2^2 = S_1^2 C^2 + C_1^2 S^2 + K S_1^2 S^2 \sin^2 \gamma_1 - 2 C C_1 S S_1 \cos \gamma_1 .$$

Now if we define the two small parameters

$$\kappa_i = \frac{S_i}{C_i} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma = \frac{\kappa}{\kappa_i} ,$$

we can rewrite S_2 as

$$S_2 = (S_1 C) (1 + \sigma^2 + K \kappa^2 \sin^2 \gamma_1 - 2 \sigma \cos \gamma_1)^{\frac{1}{2}} ,$$

allowing therefore to express $\cos(\theta)$ as the following

$$\cos \theta = 1 + \frac{K \kappa^2}{2} (\sigma \cos \gamma_1 - \sigma \cos^3 \gamma_1 - 1 + \cos^2 \gamma_1) .$$

At leading order, $\cos(\vartheta) \approx \cos(\theta)$, so that we can write the $c_i^{(n)}$ in terms of $\cos(\gamma_1)$ and make appear Legendre polynomials. In doing so, we obtain the following coefficients [11]:

$$\begin{aligned}
c_0^{(0)} &= L_0 \left(1 + \frac{2}{3}\beta \right) + \frac{1}{5}\beta^2 \left[L_0 + \kappa^4 \left\{ \left(\frac{4}{45}L_0 - \frac{8}{63}L_2 + \frac{4}{105}L_4 \right) \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \sigma \left(-\frac{8}{105}L_1 + \frac{16}{135}L_3 - \frac{8}{189}L_5 \right) \right\} + K\kappa^2 \left(\frac{4}{9}(L_2 - L_0) + \frac{4}{15}\sigma(L_1 - L_3) \right) \right], \\
c_0^{(1)} &= 2\beta L_0 + \frac{14}{15}\beta^2 \left[L_0 + K\kappa^2 \left(\frac{2}{7}(L_2 - L_0) - \frac{3}{70}\sigma(L_1 + 4L_3) \right) \right], \\
c_2^{(1)} &= \frac{4}{3}\beta \left[L_2 + \frac{3}{5}\sigma(L_3 - L_1) + \kappa^4 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{77}L_6 - \frac{3}{110}L_4 + \frac{1}{70}L_0 \right) + \sigma \left(-\frac{3}{35}L_1 + \frac{2}{15}L_3 - \frac{1}{21}L_5 \right) \right\} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + K\kappa^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{6}{35}L_4 - \frac{1}{14}L_2 - \frac{1}{10}L_0 \right) + \sigma \left(\frac{33}{70}L_1 - \frac{51}{70}L_3 + \frac{2}{21}L_5 \right) \right\} \right] \\
&\quad + \frac{4}{7}\beta^2 \left[L_2 + \frac{3}{5}\sigma(L_3 - L_1) + \kappa^4 \left\{ \left(-\frac{13}{630}L_0 + \frac{4}{63}L_2 - \frac{149}{2310}L_4 + \frac{5}{231}L_6 \right) \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \sigma \left(-\frac{1}{15}L_1 + \frac{134}{1485}L_3 - \frac{5}{351}L_5 - \frac{4}{429}L_7 \right) \right\} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + K\kappa^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{18}L_0 - \frac{43}{126}L_2 + \frac{2}{7}L_4 \right) + \sigma \left(\frac{89}{210}L_1 - \frac{107}{210}L_3 + \frac{2}{63}L_5 \right) \right\} \right], \\
c_0^{(2)} &= \beta^2 L_0, \\
c_2^{(2)} &= \frac{4}{21}\beta^2 \left[-L_2 + \frac{3}{5}\sigma(L_1 - L_3) + \kappa^4 \left\{ \left(\frac{3}{70}L_0 - \frac{2}{7}L_2 + \frac{27}{70}L_4 - \frac{1}{7}L_6 \right) \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \sigma \left(\frac{1}{5}L_1 - \frac{6}{55}L_3 - \frac{3}{13}L_5 + \frac{20}{143}L_7 \right) \right\} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + K\kappa^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{10}L_0 + \frac{25}{14}L_2 - \frac{66}{35}L_4 \right) + \sigma \left(-\frac{81}{70}L_1 - \frac{81}{70}L_3 + \frac{6}{7}L_5 \right) \right\} \right], \\
c_4^{(2)} &= \frac{8}{35}\beta^2 \left[L_4 + \frac{10}{9}\sigma(L_5 - L_3) + \kappa^4 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{630}L_0 - \frac{541}{3276}L_2 + \frac{633}{10010}L_4 - \frac{89}{1386}L_6 + \frac{28}{1287}L_8 \right) \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \sigma \left(\frac{1}{15}L_1 - \frac{31}{165}L_3 + \frac{7}{39}L_5 - \frac{25}{429}L_7 \right) \right\} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + K\kappa^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{21}L_2 - \frac{27}{77}L_4 + \frac{10}{33}L_6 \right) + \sigma \left(-\frac{22}{105}L_1 + \frac{793}{770}L_3 - \frac{695}{819}L_5 + \frac{70}{429}L_7 \right) \right\} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, the dipole and the quadrupole are:

$$\begin{aligned}
\xi^{(1)} &= b^2 D^2 \sigma \left[\frac{1}{5}\beta^2 \left(\frac{4}{15}K\kappa^2 - \frac{8}{105}\kappa^4 \right) \Xi_0^{(0)} - \frac{14}{15}\beta^2 \left(\frac{3}{70}K\kappa^2 \right) \Xi_0^{(1)} \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \left\{ \frac{4}{3}\beta \left(\frac{3}{5} - \frac{33}{70}K\kappa^2 + \frac{3}{35}\kappa^4 \right) + \frac{4}{7}\beta^2 \left(\frac{3}{5} - \frac{89}{210}K\kappa^2 + \frac{1}{15}\kappa^4 \right) \right\} \Xi_2^{(1)} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{4}{21}\beta^2 \left(\frac{3}{5} - \frac{81}{70}K\kappa^2 + \frac{1}{5}\kappa^4 \right) \Xi_2^{(2)} - \frac{8}{35}\beta^2 \left(\frac{22}{105}K\kappa^2 - \frac{1}{15}\kappa^4 \right) \Xi_2^{(4)} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \xi^{(2)} = & b^2 D^2 \left[\frac{1}{5} \beta^2 \left(\frac{4}{9} K \kappa^2 - \frac{8}{63} \kappa^4 \right) \Xi_0^{(0)} + \frac{14}{15} \beta^2 \left(\frac{2}{7} K \kappa^2 \right) \Xi_0^{(1)} \right. \\ & + \left. \left\{ \frac{4}{3} \beta \left(1 - \frac{1}{14} K \kappa^2 \right) + \frac{4}{7} \beta^2 \left(1 - \frac{43}{126} K \kappa^2 + \frac{4}{63} \kappa^4 \right) \right\} \Xi_2^{(1)} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{4}{21} \beta^2 \left(-1 + \frac{25}{14} K \kappa^2 - \frac{2}{7} \kappa^4 \right) \Xi_2^{(2)} + \frac{8}{35} \beta^2 \left(\frac{1}{21} K \kappa^2 - \frac{541}{3276} \kappa^4 \right) \Xi_2^{(4)} \right] \end{aligned}$$

χ is encoded in σ and κ . The evolution of the l-multipoles with χ is to be studied to obtain a well defined theoretical prediction of the ratio evolution in curved space. In particular, $\Omega_{K,0}$ intervenes through the physical distance r separating the objects, that is no longer related to the coordinate χ through the constant c/H_0 but rather as

$$r = \frac{c}{H_0 |\Omega_{K,0}|^{-1/2}} \chi.$$

5.4 Alcock-Paczyński test

The empirical evolution of the ratio $\xi^{(1)}/\xi^{(2)}$, as depicted in figure 13, was derived under the assumption of a specific cosmology, with parameters $\Omega_{m,0} = 0.32$ and $H_0 = 67 \text{ km.s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. This evolution (with respect to χ) was found to align well with the theoretical prediction. However, it raises the question of whether this alignment would persist under a different cosmological model. If the dipole and quadrupole change in the same way across different cosmologies, the ratio evolutions would remain unchanged regardless of the cosmological assumptions. Conversely, if the dipole and quadrupole exhibit different behaviors under varying cosmologies, we might expect some ratio evolutions corresponding to certain cosmologies to deviate more from the theoretical prediction, while others align more closely. Since the theoretical prediction is independent of the cosmology employed, the cosmology that yields the ratio evolution most closely matching the theoretical prediction may be the "right" cosmology, the one that truly governs our universe.

Thus, we measured again the ratio for different values of χ in the same way as we did to obtain the results in figure 13 but with changing $\Omega_{m,0}$ to test different cosmologies. The value of H_0 was kept unchanged in this study because changes in H_0 would apply an isotropic scaling to distances, affecting them uniformly in all directions (both radial and tangential). This means that varying H_0 would not alter the anisotropic features we are analyzing, that is the dipole-to-quadrupole ratio of the correlation function in redshift space. By expressing distances in $h^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$, we effectively normalize them with respect to H_0 , making the resulting measurements independent of H_0 . Therefore, the evolution of the dipole-to-quadrupole ratio as a function of the distance between surveyed objects remains unaffected by changes in H_0 , allowing us to focus on the impact of $\Omega_{m,0}$.

On figure 14, we can see that indeed, the most aberrant cosmology, the one for which $\Omega_{m,0} = 0.5$, is the one that deviates the most from the theoretical evolution, followed by $\Omega_{m,0} = 0.4$ which is aberrant as well. On the other hand, the cosmologies that match the best the prediction are the most realistic ones, i.e. $\Omega_{m,0} = 0.32$ and $\Omega_{m,0} = 0.28$. Further tests can be done with different values of $\Omega_{m,0}$ around 0.3 and more points and a χ^2 test can be performed to determine the cosmology that gives the best fit to the theoretical ratio. Regarding the data reported on figure 14, the cosmology that minimizes the χ^2 statistic, taking into account only the first 3 points for each one, is the $\Omega_{m,0} = 0.32$ cosmology.

Figure 14: Evolution of the ratio $R = \xi^{(1)}/\xi^{(2)}$ multiplied by $5\chi_1(z=1)/3$ w.r.t χ for different cosmologies.

6 Conclusion

The primary objective of this project was to determine whether the Euclid satellite could detect a potential curvature of the universe. To ensure a thorough and accurate analysis, wide-angle effects were considered, which have been shown to significantly influence the odd multipoles of the correlation function by making them non-zero. Additionally, the ratio of the dipole to the quadrupole was theoretically demonstrated to simplify to a straightforward expression in the case of a flat universe, specifically $\frac{3}{5} \frac{r}{r_1}$. Given its simplicity and inclusion of wide-angle effects, this ratio was selected as the key metric for analyzing the catalogues and addressing the project's central question. The methodology involved measuring the empirical ratio and assessing how many observations would be necessary to reduce errors sufficiently for its detectability. Results showed that 2 observations are enough, meaning that a volume twice bigger than the one actually surveyed by Euclid is necessary to detect the ratios. According to current projections, Euclid will be surveying a volume of this size by 2027.

In case of curvature, the expected evolution of the ratio is still to be determined by studying the evolutions of the l -multipoles $\Xi_l^{(n)}$, including for different values of $\Omega_{K,0}$.

Moreover, this study allowed to infer a very interesting feature of the ratio, that is its dependence over the cosmology and more precisely the value of $\Omega_{m,0}$, opening the window for the possibility to use the latter to gain insights into the right value of $\Omega_{m,0}$.

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